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REHABILITATION OF PATIENTS WITH EXTERNAL GENITAL ENDOMETRIOSIS AFTER SURGICAL TREATMENT

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ABSTRACT

The effectiveness of anti-relapse therapy has been confirmed by all gynecological communities involved in the study of endometriosis. When carrying out hormone therapy, it should be borne in mind that endometriosis is a chronic disease with a recurrent course and signs of autonomous growth of the implant. The gold standard for diagnosis is laparoscopy of the pelvic organs under general anesthesia. Laparoscopy may be diagnostic, therapeutic, or both.

Keywords: Endometriosis, COC, treatment of endometriosis, genital organs, laparoscopic revision of uterine.

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РЕАБИЛИТАЦИИ ПАЦИЕНТОК С НАРУЖНЫМ ГЕНИТАЛЬНЫМ ЭНДОМЕТРИОЗОМ ПОСЛЕ ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Эффективность противорецидивной терапии подтверждена всеми гинекологическими сообществами, занимающимися изучением эндометриоза. При проведении гормональной терапии следует учитывать, что эндометриоз представляет собой хроническое заболевание с рецидивирующим течением и признаками автономного роста имплантата. Золотым стандартом диагностики является лапароскопия органов малого таза под общим наркозом. Лапароскопия может быть диагностической, терапевтической или и той, и другой.

Ключевые слова: Эндометриоз, КОК, лечение эндометриоза, генитальные органы, лапароскопия органов малого таза.

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JARROHLIK DAVOLASHDAN KEYIN TASHQI GENITAL ENDOMETRIOZLI BEMORLARNI REABILITATSIYA QILISH

ANNOTATSIYA

Antiaretsidiv terapiyaning samaradorligi endometriozni o'rganish bilan shug'ullanadigan barcha ginekologik jamoalar tomonidan tasdiqlangan. Gormon terapiyasini o'tkazishda endometrioz takrorlanuvchi yo'l bilan surunkali kasallik va implantning avtonom o'sishi belgilari ekanligini yodda tutish kerak. Tashxis qo'yishning oltin standarti umumiy behushlik ostida tos a'zolarining laparoskopiyasi hisoblanadi. Laparoskopiya diagnostik, terapevtik yoki ikkalasi ham bo'lishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: Endometrioz, kok, endometriozni davolash, genital a'zolar, kichik chanoq ichki a'zolari laparoskopiyasi.

Introduction.

Endometriosis is a chronic inflammatory disease affecting 6-10% of women of reproductive age. This is determined by the presence of endometrial-like tissue outside the uterus (lesions), usually affecting the pelvis and ovaries [1,2]. Although it is as common as back pain, it is poorly understood, and treatment and diagnosis are often delayed [2]. For example, in the United Kingdom, there is an average delay in accessing endometriosis treatment for 7-9 years [3]. This is largely due to the lack of accurate, non-invasive diagnostic tests or biomarkers [4]. The gold standard of diagnosis is laparoscopy of the pelvic organs under general anesthesia. Laparoscopy can be diagnostic, therapeutic, or both. Delays in diagnosis lead to unnecessary suffering, and endometriosis is associated with debilitating pelvic pain, infertility and fatigue and can have devastating consequences for the quality of life. Endometriosis is not treatable, but there are a number of treatment options. These include drugs that suppress ovarian function (which may have side effects [5]) or surgical intervention for lesions (usually laparoscopically). Surgical removal is often considered the best treatment option for symptomatic endometriosis [6], but it does not reduce pain in 20-28% of patients who underwent surgery [7,8].

Variable response to surgery

Quantifying the potential for improvement of symptoms in a woman after surgery is important for making clinical decisions and developing treatment strategies. Secondary results of observational single-center studies indicate a differentiated response to pain reduction after surgery to remove endometriosis, which is inversely proportional to the severity of the disease [8-11]. One randomized controlled trial (RCT) showed that pain symptoms improved after endometriosis surgery in significantly more patients with moderate and mild endometriosis (approximately 100% and 70%, respectively) than with minimal disease (approximately 40%) [9]. In 2 other studies, women with deep endometriosis experienced a greater reduction in pain after surgery than women with superficial endometriosis [10,11].

Although WHO recommends that women undergo therapeutic laparoscopy for complicated endometriosis in specialized centers, but since we do not have scientifically based information for the clinical recognition of these women. We are also currently unable to determine which women will respond to this treatment. As a result, therapeutic laparoscopy, an expensive and limited resource with long waiting lists, is not necessarily performed by those who will experience pain reduction.

The factors predicting pain reduction after endometriosis surgery have not yet been properly identified, as they have never been studied as a major research issue. However, secondary results of previous tests indicate that such factors can be identified [8,9,11]. Our goal is to eliminate the existing gap by predicting success by reducing pain after endometriosis surgery.

The purpose of the study:

To develop models of clinical prediction of endometriosis to answer 2 fundamental questions concerning surgical treatment of endometriosis:

1. Which women with confirmed endometriosis benefit from surgery and see an improvement in pain and quality of life?
2. Is it possible to identify these women based on clinical symptoms measured before laparoscopy?

Research objectives

1. To conduct a systematic review of preoperative and intraoperative factors associated with the success of postoperative treatment of endometriosis.
2. To conduct a systematic review of clinical risk factors associated with endometriosis.
3. Develop and validate clinical prediction models to predict changes in self-assessment of pain and quality of life after surgery in women with confirmed (primary models) or suspected (secondary models) diagnosis of endometriosis.
4. Describe the implementation plan within the secondary medical care program for women with a confirmed or suspected diagnosis of endometriosis using joint design workshops.

Results

Drug therapy is used in the form of self-treatment and in order to prevent relapses after surgical treatment. The effectiveness of anti-relapse therapy has been confirmed by all gynecological communities involved in the study of endometriosis. When carrying out hormone therapy, it should be borne in mind that endometriosis is a chronic disease with a recurrent course and signs of autonomous growth of the implant. No medication eliminates the morphological substrate of endometriosis, exerting only a temporary indirect effect on its biological activity. Hormone therapy is based on a decrease in estrogen levels, which leads to a decrease in the size of endometrioid formations and the frequency of relapses of endometriosis. Barbieri research in 1992 the optimal threshold concentration of estrogens in the blood serum (30-60 pc/ml) was determined, which, on the one hand, suppresses the growth of endometriosis foci, on the other hand, prevents the appearance of signs of hypoestrogenism, provides stable bone mineral density (BMD) [14]. Currently, the following drugs are most often used for the treatment of patients with endometriosis:

1. Combined oral contraceptives (COCs). They have been used for more than 50 years. The positive aspects are: low cost, the possibility of long-term and repeated use, as well as the contraceptive effect, which is important for young and sexually active women. COCs have long and firmly occupied a certain "niche" in the treatment of endometriosis, namely, the relief of dysmenorrhea and, above all, algomenorrhea (effectiveness — 60-95%). For treatment, drugs containing dienogest as a progestogenic component are used (dienogest — 2 mg, ethinyl estradiol — 0.03 mg). The method of application is being discussed, but many prefer to prescribe the drug in a continuous mode, which ensures the absence of a menstrual-like reaction. According to P. Vercellini et al., COCs after endometrioma removal reduce the risk of relapse or lengthen the duration of the post-relapse period [9]. However, recently there has been evidence that COCs do not properly stop the pain symptom and dyspareunia, and their appointment for dysmenorrhea correlates with surgically confirmed endometriosis in subsequent years, and in the case of prescribing these drugs for severe primary dysmenorrhea — with deep invasive forms of endometriosis [15]. The presence of an estrogenic component in the composition of COCs for the treatment of endometriosis — certainly an estrogen—dependent disease - is also being discussed, which makes us pay attention to other medications, the effectiveness of which is supported by evidence.

2. Antigonadotropins. For many years, the drugs of choice for the treatment and rehabilitation of patients with endometriosis have been gonadotropin-releasing hormone (aH-RG) agonists with antiestrogenic, antigestagenic, antigonadotropic and antiandrogenic effects. High clinical efficacy and ease of use (3-6 injections) of drugs: goserelin acetate depot 3.6 mg, busarelin acetate depot 3.93 mg, leuprorelin acetate depot 3.75 mg, triptorelin acetate depot 3.75 mg have caused their predominant use in recent decades. However, the high cost and the presence of serious side effects of AH-RG associated with an induced severe estrogen deficiency condition (headaches, irritability, dry skin, increased blood pressure, sleep disorders, increased sweating, hot flashes, decreased libido, weight gain by an average of 5%, decreased bone mineral density, decreased ovarian reserve), necessitated the use of recurrent therapy with hormone replacement therapy in the most severe cases, and also predetermined the search for alternative drugs with similar effectiveness. Limited in time (3 and no more than 6 months) and, as a rule, their single use also limits the possibilities of using aG-RG mainly by postoperative rehabilitation.

3. Progestogens. Levonorgestrel-the secreting intrauterine system of Mirena contains 52 mg of levonorgestrel with a daily release of 20 micrograms of the drug directly into the endometrium.

Levonorgestrel is a synthetic progestogen from the group of 19-norsteroids — one of the most potent progestins with maximum biological activity and pronounced antiestrogenic, antigonadotropic effect, weak androgenic effect. High concentrations of levonorgestrel in the endometrium contribute to a decrease in the sensitivity of its estrogenic and progesterone receptors, having a strong antiproliferative effect. High clinical efficacy, ease of use (single administration of the intrauterine system for up to 5 years), the absence of serious side effects during treatment predetermines the "niche" of using this drug for endometriosis — patients with dysmenorrhea and pain symptoms of late reproductive age who are not planning pregnancy (improving quality of life). Disadvantages — the possibility of infectious complications associated with the use of any intrauterine devices. Dienogest — a 4th generation progestogen (a combination of 19 nortestosterone and progesterone derivatives) at a dose of 2 mg /day was specially developed for the treatment of endometriosis. The bioavailability of the drug exceeds 90%. Positive aspects: effective progestogenic effect on endometrioid tissue in the absence of significant androgenic, glucocorticoid effects (hot flashes, decreased BMD), suppression of ovulation with a moderate decrease in estradiol synthesis, the levels of which are within the "therapeutic window" Barbieri). The drug has an antiproliferative and anti-inflammatory effect on endometrial and endometrioid stromal cells, an antiangiogenic effect (in experimental studies). Dienogest is the only progestin that, at a low dose, has demonstrated similar efficacy to aH-RG. The drug effectively relieves pain caused by endometriosis: dysmenorrhea, dyspareunia, chronic pelvic pain due to atrophy of endometrioid foci [16, 18]. Dienogest is also suitable for long-term use due to its favorable safety profile and tolerability. Although the drug is not yet licensed for contraception, the results of studies that studied the effect of dienogest at a dose of 2 mg / day on ovulation show that the drug causes complete anovulation. Comparison of dienogest (2 mg/day) with various forms of aH-RG (depot of leuprolide acetate at a dose of 3.75 mg/m every 4 weeks, depot of triptorelin at a dose of 3.75 mg/m monthly and intranasal form of buserelin at a dose of 900 mcg/day) [17-19] reliably demonstrated equal clinical efficacy of the two methods of treatment (agonists and progestogen) with better progestogen tolerance (hot flashes and a decrease in bone mineral density were significantly more common in the treatment of AH-RG), which makes dienogest the drug of choice for the treatment of endometriosis, including long-term.

Conclusions: Thus, both methods of treatment of endometriosis — medical and surgical — should be considered not as competing, but as combined, expanding the tactical arsenal of the doctor, and the individual choice of the optimal (depending on the clinical situation) medical and surgical component increases the effectiveness of treatment and improves the prognosis.

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